

DAMAGE LOCATION USING A LOW-COST RESISTANCE-BASED SENSOR SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the results of experimental studies concerned with low-velocity impact damages of carbon fibre composites by measurement of resistance change due to the damage. Interlayers of an Epoxy resin film were employed in order to electrically isolate the sensing plies from the rest of the composite enabling damage location and quantification. Impact damage was also examined using two other techniques, sample sectioning and X – Radiography, as a comparison. The results indicated that the damage sizes measured from these three techniques were similar. Therefore, the success of prediction of impact damage by measuring resistance, which is the major concern of this research, is validated by the comparison with conventional techniques from X-ray to sample sectioning.

Key Terms: Smart sensors, Damage detection, Resistance changes, Impact damage.

INTRODUCTION

Carbon fibre reinforced composites (CFRC) are finding increasing application in many demanding areas, such as the aerospace and automotive industries. Due to their specific strength and stiffness to weight ratios, they are gaining wider acceptance and tending to replace conventional materials in many structural applications. However, one of the major factors limiting the potential applications of composites is the susceptibility of the materials to low velocity impact damages as the consequence of dropped tools etc. The situation becomes crucial as the internal damages are barely visible, which will potentially degrade the mechanical properties, such as compressive strength, dramatically. Research has, therefore, been carried out to analyse the measurement of impact damage using conventional ways of X-ray [1, 2], C-scan [3-7] integrated optical fibres sensors [8-15] and computational numerical evaluation of the impact damages using a self-sensing system that monitors the electrical properties of the reinforcing fibres [16-22].

BACKGROUND

Low-velocity impact damages

Low-velocity impact causes three basic types of damage in laminated carbon fibre reinforced composites, namely matrix crack, delamination and fibre breakage, which can significantly reduce the mechanical properties. Under through thickness impact loading, local cracks are initiated in the matrix and rapidly grow until they cause delamination between 0° and 90° plies. With the increase of the load, the delaminated area soon propagates, followed by the occurrence of fibre breakages. The complete failure of laminated composites occurs as the load reaches a critical level sufficient to cause extensive fibre failure. It has been demonstrated [23] that delamination only occurs at the interfaces of laminates with different fibre orientation and it seems that delamination is initiated from matrix cracks, which are the initial damage. To successfully monitor impact damage, it is necessary to detect at least delamination and fibre fracture, as these are the most detrimental damage modes to composite properties.

The principle of self-sensing

In this paper, the self - sensing ability of the composite involves the measurements of changes in the resistance of the composite caused by the deformation of the structural material itself. CFRC contains carbon fibres, which can act as electrical conductors embedded in an insulating matrix. Therefore, a change of resistance (ΔR) of the composite can be expected when the conducting path (fibres) are modified by the damage development under an external destructive influence. The current flow can go through either a single fibre or nearby fibres by inter-fibre contact points (IFCPs). As far as IFCPs are concerned, the current flow will become more metallic as the number of IFCPs increase and any changes due to damage will be lower. Therefore, the change of R is a function of fibre orientation and volume fraction of fibres. This is shown schematically in figure 1. There is no change of R unless most of the fibres are broken when multilayer composites are used. However, in a single unidirectional layer, the electrical properties are highly anisotropic, this is because IFCPs have higher resistance than the fibres themselves. Because of this, the sensor in the current study uses an interleaf film to electrically isolate the sensing plies from the rest of the composite, ensuring that the anisotropic properties are preserved. This enables sensing of damage due to localised resistance changes.

Figure 1.
principle of

Electrical
smart system

The aim of this paper

This paper aims to study experimental data for low-velocity impact damage at various impact energies obtained from the measurement of resistance of the sample (with resin films as an interlayer). The results are compared with similar results from X-radiographs and the sectioning of samples to provide a reference of the damage level.

EXPERIMENTAL

Sample preparation

Specimens were fabricated using carbon-fibre/epoxy laminates (CIBA GEIGY FIBREDUX: 913C-HTA (121e)-5-346) with stacking sequence:

- $[0_1/C/0_1/R/0_2/90_8/0_2/R/0_2]$
- $[0_1/C/0_1/R/90_1/C/90_1/R/0_3/90_6/0_3/90_2/0_2]$

Note: C – Contacts; R – Resin films.

Figure 2 illustrates a typical stacking sequence of the cross-ply laminates.

Figure 2. Schematic illustration of the manner in which contact pairs and resin plies were introduced.

The contact spacing was 3mm for the laminate: $[0_1/C/0_1/R/90_1/C/90_1/R/0_3/90_6/0_3/90_2/0_2]$

Note: only part of the stacking sequence has been shown in this figure: $[0_1/C/0_1/R/90_1/C/90_1/R/0_3/90$

The specimens were made by hand with copper signal wire contacts (with contact spacing of 3 mm) embedded near impact surface. The resin films, which are compatible with the pre-preg, were added into the stacking sequence being regarded as an interlayer for the purpose of electrical insulation. Samples were cured in an autoclave with the cure schedule of increasing T to 120°C at the speed of 2°C/min and being held for 1 hour, which is followed by cooling to room temperature.

Impact testing

The impact testing was carried out using an un-instrumented Davenport falling – dart drop tower with 10mm diameter hemispherical tup. The sample was impacted repeatedly with a progressive increase of dropping weight, varying from 1.6J to 16.9J. The resistance across each pair of contacts (as shown in figure 2, following the fibre orientation) for both 0° and 90° was measured at each level of impact energy until the complete failure of the sample. The data obtained can, therefore be compared with the original measurement, which was made prior to impact loading, in order to determine the size and location of the damage.

Sample sectioning

An easy but effective way of destructively measuring impact damage is to polish the sample through the damaged area. The samples were then investigated using optical microscopy with photographs being taken, facilitating measurement. Polishing through the cross sectioning was carried out with an interval of 2mm, the orientation being parallel to the 0° direction. Therefore, by repeating this process, detailed pictures of the damage configuration through the whole sample can be obtained.

X – radiography

This technique has been well developed [1, 2] and shown to be suitable for detection of defects at sample's surface, subsurface or even internal cracks. It can, therefore be regarded as a good comparison for the self-sensing technique and the polishing of samples, due to its very good indication of damage size and location. In this study the ZnI₂ based penetrant was introduced by drilling a hole with diameter of 1mm into the centre of the damaged zone. The penetrant was then applied and allowed it to penetrate the entire damage zone, being left over night for penetration to occur.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Impact testing

The results of resistance measurements at varying levels of impact loading show that the geometry employed in this study is capable of identifying the impact damage induced in the samples. For instance, Fig. 3 illustrates the result from a cross-ply laminate with contact density of 3mm. The central part, with contacts 11 and 12, demonstrates a distinct change of R compared with the rest indicating significant damage, probably fibre breakages, occurred in this region. Furthermore, unlike contacts 11 and 12, it is interesting to note that contacts around the central damage area undergo a small decrease of R. It is possible that compressive damages induced by impact damage in through-thickness direction cause re-arrangement of inter-fibre contact points and results in this fall of R. It is also possible that the occurrence of delamination reduces the stress on the ply and the resistance falls, because the fibres are piezo – resistive, with a change in stress-state changing their resistance. The fall therefore appears to be associated with damage other than fibre fracture. This factor was used as an effective way of predicting the size of the impact damage, since it can be regarded as a pre-show or secondary effect of the consequence of impact. Because the significant change of R can not be observed unless the fibres around the contact are broken, but the damage sequence starts with matrix cracks followed by delamination, the decrease of R is, therefore the indication of the more extensive matrix damage zone.

The size of impact damage predicted by this technique was determined for each impact energy and recorded for comparison with the other techniques, as indicated in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Impact damage test for cross-ply laminates with sensor density of 3mm indicating damage size of $55.5 \pm 1.5\text{mm}$ for energy level of 9.3 J (Sensors: 3-21)
 $34.5 \pm 1.5\text{mm}$ for energy level of 4.4 J (Sensors: 6-17)

Sample sectioning

Using this technique, damage development has been revealed by polishing the sample through its cross areas with interval of 2mm. Figure 4 shows typical micrographs obtained from the sample with induced impact loading at 8.0J. By reviewing the cross-sectional area under an optical microscope with a magnification of $50\times$, it appears that cracks start from intraply matrix splitting including shear

cracks, which are followed by delamination (only occurred at surface between 0° and 90° for cross ply laminates) generated by these cracks, then fibre breakage as indicated by the significant change of resistance.

Under the microscope, the distribution of the delaminated area was extended with the increase of impact energy and the area does show that the size of damage can be determined easily. Observation was made with different levels of impact energies starting from 4.4, 6.7, and 8.0 to 9.3 J and the dimensions were recorded. From re-assembling of pictures for different impact levels, all damage areas showed a similar peanut shape with increasing size as loading increases; however the damage shapes appear unbalanced at the beginning of delamination. This has been shown in figure 5.

Figure 4. Demonstration of intraply matrix splitting cracks and delamination with different magnification: a) 50× b) 100×

Figure 5. Unbalanced shape of damage area from picture re-assembling

X – radiography

X – radiography, is a well developed tool for detection of the location and length of cracks allowing measurement of the damage area. Figure 6 shows a typical radiograph of the impacted region with loading energy of 4.4 J and 9.3 J.

Discussion

Table 1 gives a summary of results from the 3 different types of techniques applied for the measurement of impact damage zone size. It can be seen that all of the techniques give a very comparable measured level of damage. Generally, sample polishing gives the highest indicated

damage zone, while X-ray is fairly similar to it. The zone predicted by the self – sensing technique is smaller than the others, but the difference is low when compared with these two conventional ways, at maximum of 15% at energy level of 6.7 J. It can therefore be seen that the self – sensing arrangement shown in this paper gives a reliable method of measuring the impact zone sizes in carbon fibre composites.

Dimension: (mm)
 Length: 36.8
 Width: 20.5 (bigger part);
 4.8 (small part)

Dimension: (mm)
 Length: 53.3
 Width: 21.9 (bigger part);
 19.9 (small part)

Figure 6. X – radiographic photos with impact energies of 4.4 and 9.3 J

Energy level (Joules)	Effective measurement of damage scale		
	X – ray (mm)	Sample polishing (mm)	R (mm)
4.4	36.8	38 ± 3	34.5 ± 1.5
6.7	47.6	49 ± 4	40.5 ± 1.5
8.0	53.3	55 ± 5	46.5 ± 1.5
9.3	58.8	58 ± 3	55.5 ± 1.5

Table 1. Comparison of damage areas measured using the three techniques

CONCLUSIONS

Results obtained from this study (table 1) revealed that the technique of measurement of the change of resistance is not only able to detect impact damage but also is an accurate way of predicting the location and size of damage zone with its error of 15 % (4 % for energy level of 9.3 J). Moreover, this technique, unlike sample polishing that is destructive or X – radiography that involves complicated equipment, processes and skilled technician, is easy to apply with only measurement of the change of resistance being required. This technique of monitoring carbon fibre reinforced composite is therefore a significant technique for the measurement and prediction of impact damage

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